

Cefalópodes coleóides e suas habilidades cognitivas, uma revisão

Coleoid cephalopods and their cognitive abilities, a review

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Resumo: Um campo crescente de estudo é a Etologia Cognitiva, que foca em pesquisas de comportamento animal que vai além do inato, como suas capacidades cognitivas e suas culturas. Esses estudos ajudam a propagar a educação ambiental e a sensibilização sobre os feitos desses animais. Os cefalópodes colóides (lulas, polvos e sépias) desenvolveram uma capacidade cognitiva comparável a de vertebrados por conta da perda de suas conchas externas e dos desafios ecológicos e sociais que enfrentam. Neste estudo foi feito um levantamento bibliográfico que exemplifica as habilidades apresentadas por esses animais. As habilidades vistas nestes três grupos mostram que eles são capazes de raciocínio causal, imaginação, plasticidade comportamental, prospecção, e reconhecimento no espelho. De acordo com o que foi analisado, é possível concluir que os cefalópodes colóides possuem uma teoria de mente e uma consciência de maior ordem, assim como vários vertebrados considerados inteligentes, como primatas e corvídeos.

Palavras Chave: cognição animal, cefalópodes colóides, consciência, etologia cognitiva.

Abstract: A growing field of study is Cognitive Ethology, which focuses on research into animal behavior that goes beyond the innate, such as their cognitive abilities and cultures. These studies help with environmental education and spread awareness of the deeds of these animals. Coleoid cephalopods (squid, octopus and cuttlefish) have developed a cognitive capacity comparable to that of vertebrates because of the loss of their external shells and the ecological and social challenges they face. In this study, a literary review was carried out to exemplify the abilities presented by these animals. The skills seen in these three groups show that they are capable of causal reasoning, imagination, and behavioral plasticity, foresight, and mirror recognition. According to what has been analyzed, it is possible to conclude that coleoid cephalopods present theory of mind and higher order consciousness, as do several vertebrates considered intelligent, such as primates and corvids.

Key words: animal cognition, coleoid cephalopods, consciousness, cognitive ethology.

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1. Introdução

Ethology is an old field of study. Learning animal behavior was essential for our ancestors to survive. Today, understanding animal behavior can have practical applications in various fields (Alcook, 2011), such as pollination, agriculture or animal rehabilitation. The field of Ethology has evolved from its classic era, where only the innate behavior was observed and described, to a more multidiscipline subject, working alongside physiology, psychology and ecology (Shettleworth, 2011). One of the newest fields of study in Ethology is Cognitive Ethology, which has the objective of being a comparative, evolutive and ecological study of non-human animal minds; including mental processes, rationalities, information processing and consciousness (Bekoff, 1995).

Animal cognition can be defined according to Shettleworth (2011) as all the different ways in which animals receive information about the world according to their senses. How they process information, integrate and decide to act upon them. Cognition includes perception, learning, memory and decision-making. However, the author goes on to explain that cognitive ethology is the only field in which you cannot be sure of an animal's consciousness, since animals will never be able to report verbally their experiences and corroborate that they have, in fact, some level of it. Nevertheless, there are a few exceptions to this rule.

One exception was seen in 1972, when scientist Francine Patterson started to teach the gorilla Hanabi-Ko (*Gorilla gorilla*), or Koko, American Sign Language (ASL). Koko learned around 900 signs and was able to make up phrases of up to eight words to communicate with Francine (Hanley, 2004). For three decades, Koko was able to report episodes that happened in present and past time, to report her emotional state and construct rhymes with the understanding of human verbal phonetics. Koko even showed some type of humor by understanding the other's perspective and using it to "play" with their emotional state (Patterson & Linden, 1981).

Certainly, it could be argued that this clear demonstration of consciousness coming from Koko, and all the other gorillas that participated in Project Koko later on, happens because of the closely related phylogenetic and evolution between the *Homo sapiens* and *Gorilla gorilla*. However, in July of 2012, an international group of scientists, specialists in the fields of cognitive neuroscience, neuropharmacology, neurophysiology, neuroanatomy and computational neuroscience, got together at the University of Cambridge, in the United Kingdom, to reevaluate the neurobiological substrates necessary for the experience of consciousness and the behaviors related to it in human and non-human animals (Low et al., 2012).

This group signed a documented declaring:

"The absence of a neurocortex does not seem to stop an organism of experiencing emotional states. Converging evidence indicates that non-human animals have the neuroanatomical, neurochemical and neurophysiological substrates necessary to generate the different states of consciousness, along with the ability to perform intentional behavior. Consequently, the weight of evidence shows that humans are not the only ones to possess the neurological substrates that generate consciousness. Non-human animals, including all mammals and birds, along with other creatures like octopus, also possess these neurological substrates." (Low, et al., 2021, p.2)

The coleoid cephalopod (octopus, squid and cuttlefish) is the group of interest of this review. They are invertebrates that belong in the Phylum Mollusca, Class Cephalopoda (Cepha = head, poda = feet), and Subclass *Coleoidea*. Their fossil records date to the Cambrian Period (approximately 500 million years ago). Coleoid cephalopods make up the most diverse group of cephalopods today, in comparison to its sister-group Nautiloidea, which contains only five species of nautiloids. The most unmistakable difference between nautiloids and coleoids is the presence of external shell in the nautiloids, used for floating and protection, and the presence of internal shells in coleoids. Cuttlefish have a small curved shell, completely wrapped by its mantle. Squid have only a feather shaped, proteic shell also wrapped by its mantle, called a pen. Octopi on the other hand, have completely lost their shell (Hickman, Roberts & Keen, 2016).

Image 1. The picture above shows the different shells of cephalopods. 1. Nautilus, external shell; 2. Belemnite, extinct, internal shell; 3. Cuttlefish of the genus *Spirula*, has an internal shell in the shape of a spiral; 4. Cuttlefish of the genus *Sepia*, internal shell in an oval shape; 5. Squid of the genus *Loligo*, internal shell in the shape of a feather. 6. Octopus, do not have a shell (Gray, 2003).

the non-random chromatophore activity presents a pattern that can be compared to a vertebrate's REM sleep pattern (Frank et al., 2012).

In cephalopod coleoid physiology, three main nervous system centers can be identified, each one controlling a different area and integrating information coming from the environment. **(1) The brain**, which is responsible for decision making and the processing and learning of what is gathered in a sensitive capacity (Mather & Dickel, 2017). **(2) The arms** which are used for exploration and action, be it exploration in the chemical-sensitive capacity, capturing visual information, proprioceptive exploration and/or foraging. The arms use the suckers to grab and move, to travel in the water and land, to manipulate objects that can be used as tools and to hunt for prey. Still, it is notable, that each octopus has a favorite arm, which they use for exploration (Mather & Dickel, 2017). Cephalopod **(3) skin** has its own nervous and muscular systems for the rapid and sophisticated control of its pigmented cells, the chromatophores. Which can be used to change the coloration and texture to camouflage with the environment and avoid predators, manipulate or attract prey and communicate with others. The camouflage adopted by this group is dynamic, since the patterns created are controlled by neurons. Octopi and Cuttlefish can copy contrast, texture and the color of their environment, even when they are considered colorblind for only having one photopigment. Their camouflage abilities also depend on previous experiences. Animals with a history of being in more stimulating environments have better abilities than those without it (Mather & Dickel, 2017).

For the control on all three fronts to be possible (1, 2, 3), the neural structures must also be divided in three big areas: the subesophage lobes are responsible for the control of homeostasis, like heartbeat, breathing, etc. In the lobes of the supraesophageal ganglion region is where higher learning happens. The lobes are subdivided in regions for learning with chemical-sensitive receptors and visual receptors that contribute to complex behavior. The mangnocelular lobe is responsible for chromatophore control and flight responses through the contraction of the mantle. Furthermore, we have the vertical lobe complex, which can be functionally compared to the hippocampus complex in vertebrates, thus the vertical lobe also has an integratory function (Grasso & Basil, 2009). This general structure of the nervous system of cephalopods is greatly associated to octopi; however, other coleoids share these structures in different proportions. For example, squid show a 300% increase in the volume of the optic lobe in comparison to the octopus, exhibiting physiological coherencies with their life strategies as visual predators of pelagic regions (Grasso & Basil, 2009). A study was made, mapping the squid brain, using a MRI machine. It confirmed the hypothesis of the functional interactions between the different lobes. Fluorescent neural tracers showed 145 new pathways in the squid's brain, beyond the ones that were already known (Chung, Kurnianwan & Marshall,

Another important characteristic of the coleoid cephalopod is its highly varied behavior, which is directly related to a centralized nervous system and highly developed sensory organs. These animals have the biggest brains amongst invertebrates (Hickman, Roberts, & Keen, 2016) and neurological structures similar to mammals (Shigeno, et al., 2018). There are studies that indicate that the neural structures of cephalopods have a level of complexity and subdivision on the basal lobe that indicates to the convergence hypothesis with base ganglia of vertebrates' (Chung, Kurniawan & Marshall, 2020). Still, it was evidenced by a study that adult cuttlefish (*Sepia officinalis*) show a state of REM (Rapid Eye Movement) sleep where the arms spasm, there is eye movement and non-random chromatophore activity can be observed. The REM sleep has been observed in mammals and birds, and

2020).

The strategies of living adopted by the cephalopods say a lot about their evolution and adaptability. The hypothesis raised about the evolution of this group refers to great environmental pressures that led to the development of a level of cognition similar to vertebrate animals, especially mammals and birds. This can occur because mammals, birds and cephalopods are generalist animals, meaning they have a lot of flexibility within their ecological role and so they develop strategies, usually of high cognitive level like problem solving and use of tools, to survive (Vitti, 2013).

Another characteristic related to their survival strategy is the absence of an external shell, which allows for higher body plasticity, rapid movement through water propulsion and consequently, a more active way of life (Kroger, Vinther & Fuchs, 2011). Such way of life isn't only on the physical level but also on the cognitive level. Cephalopods need a more acute perception and consciousness of their hostile, unstable and complex environment so they can survive in a more clever way (Vitti, 2013), especially because they are prey to a large number of animals, such as cetaceans, bony fish and elasmobranchs. The cephalopods most used strategy to avoid predators is camouflage (Anderson, Mather & Wood, 2010).

One of the most accepted theories for the development of cephalopods' great cognitive capabilities is their competition with other cephalopods and invertebrates until the evolution of bony fish with which they also competed against (Grasso & Basil, 2009). The competition with *Teleostei* became known as "Packard Scenario". Both groups share several characteristics and occupy similar trophic roles in the ecological dynamic of the ecosystems they inhabit. This competitive pressure led nautiloids to disperse to deeper waters and coleoids to develop a nervous system capable of quick and efficient problem solving, this was known as "cognitive radiation" (Packard, 1972; Vitti, 2013).

Another hypothesis for the development of cephalopod's complex cognitive capabilities defends the idea that these abilities were developed from two main propellers: the Ecological Intelligence Hypothesis and the Social Intelligence Hypothesis. The behavioral flexibility, the high adaptability, the optimization of their foraging techniques and the complex cognition of these animals are directly related with the ecological challenges they face, since they are animals found "from the poles to the tropics, in shallow and deep waters" (Ikeda, 2009, p. 147) as well as the social challenges they face (Schnell, et al., 2021b; Schnell & Clayton, 2009).

It could be questioned whether cephalopod coleoids are actually social animals, however it must be remembered that squids and cuttlefish live in groups. The Caribbean-reef-squid (*Sepioteuthis sepioidea*) form well-structured groups where each member has its own ranking and placement (the bigger individuals stay on the outside, the smaller ones on the inside and one individual works as a look-out). Therefore, we can assume that squid show social behavior inside their shoal and knowing each member of the group will increase their survival and reproduction rates (Ikeda, 2009).

Octopi do not live in groups, however, they have been observed sharing the same space with conspecifics, sometimes even with one individual physically attached to another (Ikeda, 2009).

The capacity for animal cognition is a field of study that has been growing a lot through the years and has immense potential for environmental education and raising awareness, especially with the signing of the Declaration of Cambridge (Low, et al., 2012).

Image 2. 3D reconstruction of an MRI image made to observe the squid's brain. 1. Supraesophageal Region. 2. Subesophageal Region. 3. Magnocellular Lobe. 4. Optic Lobe. 5. Vertical Lobe (Chung & Kurniawan, 2020).

Sharing scientific knowledge about these animals in a playful, artistic and educational way can be used as a tool to raise discussions with the public and the scientific community about their conservation, their welfare in captivity and the ethics of their use in research.

This is important because the directive of the National Council for the Control of Animal Experimentation (CONCEA) (Brasil, 2008) in Brazil does not include any type of restriction or regulation when invertebrate animals are used in teaching, research, entertainment or economic activities. The same is true for the United States and Canada, meaning that any type of experiment can be done without consideration to the animal's husbandry, physical and/or emotional well being (Mather, 2020), even though the strong indication of its consciousness leaves us with ethical and moral obligations to minimize pain for these animals (Galhardo & Oliveira, 2006). On the other hand, in the European Union a new directive was passed, 2010/63/EU, which specifies how the animal must be kept as well as how the husbandry and handling must occur to minimize the stress caused by the protocol. The need to follow these standards will boost research on what we know about their physiology and behavior so that the protocols can stay up to date (Di Cristina, et al., 2015).

These legislative changes are made, not only because of new scientific advancement, but also because of public pressure, as was the case of the animal rights movement against cosmetic testing (Guinther, 1998). Education and awareness are necessary for the general public to take an interest in animals' well being and conservation and to make sure that their five freedoms are being respected: freedom from hunger and thirst, freedom from pain, injury or disease, freedom from discomfort, freedom to express their natural behavior and freedom from fear and distress (Vieira, 2013).

An example of ways to reach the general public is the 2021 Oscar winning documentary, *My Octopus Teacher* (Foster, Ehrlich & Reed, 2020), which shows the relationship between the filmmaker Craig Foster and a female octopus for the duration of a whole year. During that time, Foster dove with the octopus everyday and recorded its natural behavior, raising awareness and educating the public about the challenges these animals face and how the animal overcomes them. Another example is the Pixar Animation Studios film *Finding Dory* (Collins, et al., 2016). In the movie we have the character Hank, a grumpy octopus that helps the main character, Dory, in her adventures. Through the movie, facts about Hank's physiology and behavior are shown, such as the use of skin patterns to camouflage with the environment or pretend to be an object, the fact that cephalopods have three hearts, two that pump blood to the gills and one that pumps it to the rest of the body, the capacity that octopus have to open jars and their ability to move outside of water.

Image 3a. My Teacher Octopus movie poster (Foster, Ehrlich & Reed, 2020). **3b.** Finding Dory movie poster, where we can see the octopus character, Hank (Collins, et al., 2016).

Through these stories, it is possible to transport the spectator (adults and children) inside the marine world and show the challenges found there in a much more palpable way. The scientific advancements in relation to the cognitive capacities of these animals can drive these narratives and bring more awareness to conservation and the well being of these animals.

Therefore, this paper has as its objective to discuss what has already been discovered about cephalopod cognition and relate this knowledge with complex cognitive theories and consciousness theories. Furthermore, this paper aims to exemplify how these complex behaviors can also be found in other animal groups.

2. Methodology

This bibliographic review was created with articles from periodicals, magazines, book chapters and sections, all searched on platforms like Scholar Google, PubMed, Scielo, Nature, Z-Library and the digital catalogue library of Mackenzie Presbyterian University. Because of the untypical times of social isolation caused by the Covid-19 pandemic, it was not possible to do research outside of the digital area. Additionally, more articles were selected from the bibliography used in the articles found on the main research platforms mentioned above. Data from the past 50 years was selected.

The key-words used in the online research were: *cognição animal*, *desenvolvimento cognitivo*, *cognição cefalópodes*, *cognição comparativa*, *etologia cognitiva*, *animal cognition*, *cephalopod* **TABLE 1** – Cognitive abilities

studied within the different coleoid cephalopod groups and their respective references.

Cognitive Ability	Groups			Authors and Year of Publication
	Octopus	Squid	Cuttlefish	
Association learning	X	X	X	ZEPEDA, VELINE & CROOK, 2017
Discrimination learning	X	X	X	HVORECNY, et al., 2007, SPADY & WATSON, 2020
Advanced spatial learning	X	X	X	GUTNICK, et al., 2011, HVORECNY, et al., 2007
Exploratory learning	X	X	X	DARMAILLACQ, DICKEL & MATHER, 2014
Social learning (Observational learning)	X	X	X	FIORITO & SCOTTO, 1992, SAMPAIO, et al., 2020
Associative reverse learning	X		X	BUBLITZ, et al., 2017, SCHNELL, et al., 2021a
Rapid taste aversion learning			X	DARMAILLACQ, et al., 2004
Reverse learning			X	SCHNELL, et al., 2021a
Optional communication	X	X	X	BROWN, GARWOOD & WILLIAMSON, 2012, MESSENGER, 2001, SCHNELL & CLAYTON, 2019
Future-oriented behavior	X		X	BILLARD, et al., 2020; FINN, TREGENZA & NORMAN, 2009.
Appetitive conditioning	X			PAPINI & BITTERMAN, 1991
Visual discrimination	X	X		ALLEN, MICHELS & YOUNG, 1985, GUTNICK, et al., 2011
Conditional discrimination	X		X	HVORECNY, et al., 2007
Tactile discrimination	X			GUTNICK, et al., 2011
Species discrimination		X		SCHNELL & CLAYTON, 2019
Tactical deception		X	X	BROWN, GARWOOD & WILLIAMSON, 2012
Behavioral flexibility	X	X	X	SCHNELL & CLAYTON, 2019, SCHNELL, et al., 2021b
Delayed Gratification			X	SCHNELL, et al., 2021a
Individual human identification	X			ANDERSON, et al., 2010
Imprinting			X	DARMAILLACQ, CHICHERY & DICKEL, 2006, DARMAILLACQ, et al., 2006
Short term memory	X	X	X	AGIN, et al., 1998, DICKEL, CHICHERY & CHICHERY, 1998, SANDERS, 1970.
Long term memory	X	X	X	ALLEN, MICHELS & YOUNG, 1985, DICKEL, CHICHERY & CHICHERY, 1998; SANDERS, 1970, ZEPEDA, VELINE & CROOK, 2017
Source memory	X		X	BILLARD, CLAYTON & JOZET-ALVES, 2020, CROOK, 2021
Episodic memory			X	JOZET-ALVES, BERTIN & CLAYTON, 2013
Mimicry	X	X	X	BROWN, GARWOOD & WILLIAMSON, 2012, HANLON, 2007; MESSENGER, 2001
Individual personalities	X	X	X	ANDERSON, MATHER & WOOD, 2010; PRONK, WILSON & HARCOURT, 2010; SINN & MOLTSCHANIWSKYJ, 2005; ZORATTO, et al., 2018
Object permanence			X	SCHNELL, et al., 2021b
Number sense			X	HUANG, et al., 2019, YANG, CHIAO, 2016
Use of tools	X	X	X	FINN, TREGENZA & NORMAN, 2009; MATHER, 1995, MANN & PATTERSON, 2013, FOSTER, EHRLICH & REED, 2020

Cognition, cephalopod behavior, comparative cognition, comparative animal behavior, animal cognition and evolution, cognitive ethology, octopus cognition, squid cognition, cuttlefish cognition, cephalopod consciousness, octopus learning, octopus memory, squid learning, squid memory, cuttlefish learning, cuttlefish memory.

The articles were selected based on their titles and abstracts. After the initial selection, the articles went through a triage and all the information presented by the authors was organized within a table for the easy viewing of all the data

that was later discussed.

3. Results and Discussion

A total of 54 articles were analyzed in which the cognitive abilities of cephalopods were identified. Of these, 37 articles were selected to compose table 1, since they dealt directly with the abilities observed by the researchers in coleoid cephalopods. And 31 articles were also used to compose the discussion, citing examples of vertebrate animals, the skills listed in Table 1 and discussing the theories of complex cognition.

Through the contents of Table 1, it is observed that the skills of cuttlefish were the most extensively studied, since references were found for 24 of the 29 skills listed, with the octopus in second place with 20 of the 29 skills, followed by squid with 15 out of 29 skills. Certainly, more studies still need to be done in order to obtain a deeper understanding about the behavior mechanisms of these animals, considering that approximately 25% of the researched articles were published in the last three years. However, it is also arguable that their real abilities will never be clarified if the observations are limited to laboratory environments, since it is impossible to simulate the richness of ecological and social stimuli and the challenges that these animals face in the wild.

It can also be argued that many of the tests end up being subjective through the view of their authors, since we will never know exactly what it means to be an octopus, or what the complexities of a squid's life are (Safina, 2015), however it is possible to do the most to understand this without any kind of preconception already formed about animal intelligence. With that said, different ways of measuring complex cognition and intelligence in animals have already been discussed.

According to Emery and Clayton (2004), there is a basic set of skills that must be presented by an animal to ensure that it actually presents complex cognition. They are:

Causal reasoning. The process of identifying causality, the relationship between a cause and its effect (Bowers, 2021), that is, the ability to act according to an intention, to be intentional and deliberate rather than just reactionary. When the animal is able to attribute this type of reasoning to another individual, they have the ability to understand the intention of the other and thereby manipulate or deceive for its own benefit. This is called tactical deception, or Machiavellian intelligence (Emery & Clayton, 2004). The Machiavellian Intelligence Hypothesis, also called the Social Brain Hypothesis, dictates that the large brains and cognitive abilities of humans evolved because of intense social competition. Therefore, competitors needed to develop "Machiavellian" strategies to achieve greater social and reproductive success (Gavrilets & Vose, 2006).

Even though the hypothesis originated from observing human behavior on account of Niccolò Machiavelli, Machiavellian intelligence has already been observed in other animals that have complex social coexistences. Furthermore, it is argued that this social complexity is related to the large relative size of the brain in groups such as great primates, cetaceans and wolves. An example of this behavior can be seen in chimpanzees "who have been described using 'political' maneuvers to pit one competitor against another" (Byrne, 1996), and in mandrill baboons, *Mandrillus sphinx*, where a more submissive male, pretends to challenge the dominant; that way, while the dominant is showing his strength and vitality, the more submissive male uses this distraction to reproduce with the females protected by the dominant male, as seen in the first episode of the mini-series Life in Color with David Attenborough (Beaudry, et al., 2021).

Flexibility. It's the ability to act differently based on the information being received. Flexibility is one of the pillars of intelligent behavior because it requires the processing of what is being received and the ability to discover possible scenarios for what would be the best way to act (Emery & Clayton, 2004). Behavioral flexibility is considered to be the gold standard of evidence for complex cognition since causal reasoning, imagination, mental time travel and mental attribution are all pillars for behavioral flexibility to occur (Schnell, et al., 2021b). We see this when there is a difference in the pattern of foraging and migration of leatherback turtles, *Dermochelys coriacea*, which, after the nesting period, choose different locations from those they have fidelity and different times of day to forage (Hays, et al., 2006; LEA, et al., 2020).

Imagination. Imagination is the creation of scenarios and situations that cannot be perceived in the present and are, therefore created mentally. A precursor to this is object permanence. Imagination can also be perceived through insights, projection of experiences and the perspective of other individuals. An example of this is when corvids store food and can remember where food is hidden through mind mapping and object permanence. In addition, corvids can problem solve without going through the process of trial and error, demonstrating imagination and planning (Emery & Clayton, 2004).

Prospection. It's the ability to imagine future scenarios, to plan for those scenarios. We can use the same example as the one above for this, crows hiding their food. They store different types of food, with different perishable qualities, and keep in mind what food to look for and when. The crow tends to go for the food that spoils the fastest first, but if enough time passes for that food to spoil, the animal does not come back to look for it. This shows not only planning for the future but also an understanding of the passage of time (Emery & Clayton, 2004).

Coleoid cephalopods have great capacity for complex behavior because their centralized brain has a larger relative size than the brains found in reptiles and fish and comparable to birds and mammals (Ikeda, 2009), in addition to presenting all four behaviors within the skill set of Emery and Clayton (2004) (Mather & Dickel, 2017; Schnell & Clayton, 2019; Schnell, et al., 2021b).

Regarding the ecological challenges encountered by cephalopods, we can present several examples. The use of imagination and prospection in common cuttlefish (*Sepia officinalis*) that use episodic memory when hunting (Jozet-Alves, Bertin & Clayton, 2013), resuming past experiences to improve present and future experiences; in addition to having a sense of quantity and numbers since they can optimize their foraging by discriminating between quantity and quality of different prey (Schnell & Clayton, 2019).

Still in relation to foraging, the flexibility of behavior is evidenced when they make the decision on how to open the shells of their bivalve prey. The octopus can use the strength of its arms, puncture the shell or chip the edge to access the animal inside. It was also observed that octopi use these techniques on a trial and error basis for learning and there is a preference for preys that are known to be easier to open. This clearly shows decision-making by individual (Mather, 2008).

Regarding causal reasoning and flexibility, it is possible to mention mimetic, since the type of camouflage chosen comes from a decision made, an intention, because when presented with a situation, for example, confrontation with a predator, they can use different strategies, such as blending in with the environment or using bold patterns and coloring to appear bigger and more menacing. This selective signaling shows a capability for threat and risk assessment and categorization (Mather & Dickel, 2017).

When they use skin control and specific behavior to pretend to be another animal, they are using imagination through the projection of experience and perspective. Examples of this are octopi that have been reported pretending to be flounders, lionfish, and small sponges. The two-toned pygmy squid, *Idiosepius pygmaeus*, camouflages by attaching itself to algae, sea grass or debris and swinging upside down, mimicking its movement. The Caribbean-reef-squid, *Sepioteuthis sepioidea*, has been reported pretending to be the princess parrotfish, *Scarus taeniopterus* (Schnell, et al., 2021b). In relation to hunting, cephalopods use their arms in random swinging movements to attract prey and, more specifically, octopuses and cuttlefish use coloration patterns with color contrast that simulate movement, this is the passing clouds display to attract prey (Mather & Dickel, 2017).

Image 4. On the left, an octopus mimicking and acting like a flounder and on the right, a real flounder swimming (Hanlon, 2007).

The Caribbean reef squid presents flexibility of behavior in the face of threats from different species of fish; these reactions are still different from the behavior adopted for hunting. This can be seen as an ability of the squid to perceive the mental states of approaching fish, indicating mental attribution (Schnell & Clayton, 2019).

Image 5. Squid camouflaging with algae (Hanlon, Vecchione & Allcock, 2018, p. 92).

Other examples include octopi that over the course of several days used different routes when leaving their dens to hunt, avoiding places where they had explored in previous days because they know that there is a shortage of food. Furthermore, it was also observed that the common octopus, *Octopus vulgaris*, overlaps tracks already traced with a frequency of only 32%, and when returning to the burrow, it makes a direct line by means of jet propulsion. This shows examples of behavior flexibility in conjunction with imagination through the formation of cognitive maps (Msther & Kuba, 2013). Another example of a cognitive map is the ability of *O. vulgaris* to solve mazes using mainly touch (Gutnick, et al., 2011).

Image 6. Octopus using coconut shells as a refuge against predators (Finn, Tregenza & Norman, 2009).

The coconut octopus, *Amphioctopus marginatus*, has been observed carrying coconut husks as mobile dens a behavior that decreases the probability of its predation. This can be seen as a type of forward planning as the coconut shell will protect it from any future predators (Finn, Tregenza & Nirman, 2009). The use of tools for protection was also shown in the documentary *My Octopus Teacher* (Foster, Ehrlich & Reed, 2020), in which the octopus used several shells as a shield to protect itself from a shark. This shows, in addition to prospecting, mental attribution since they know that the shark is a threat (Schnell, et al., 2021b).

Still within the subject of tool use, we can mention a water jet (Mann & Patterson, 2013), as well as the use of their arms to direct objects in play, to direct prey/food (Kuba, Gutnick & Burghardt, 2014) or to demonstrate dissatisfaction with specific individuals within a laboratory or aquarium, as reported anecdotally. Play behavior shows

imagination and mental attribution that can be identified when the animal is able to distinguish between individuals (Anderson, et al., 2010).

Image 7. Octopus hiding from predator using shells as a shield (Foster, Ehrlich & Reed, 2020).

In a social context, several squid species have flexible reproduction strategies that they adopt according to the situation, for example the number of males competing. In the species *Doryteuthis opalescens*, males can be very aggressive towards females, so to protect themselves, females use their body plasticity to look like males; this strategy is adopted only by female squids in specific social conditions just like sexual mimicry in cuttlefish (Schnell & Clayton, 2019).

Image 8. Male cuttlefish (left) using tactic deception through the control of its skin to signal two conspecifics at the same time, a female (right) with whom it is trying to reproduce with and an adversary male (on the left, out of view) (Hanlon, Vecchione & Allcock, 2018, p. 167).

Male cuttlefish and squid also use a bilateral mimicry strategy. When an individual is between a competing male and a female of reproductive interest, half of this individual's body signals offensively to the male to prevent him from interfering, and the other half of the body signals the female in a receptive manner. Bilateral mimicry is considered a form of tactical deception by cuttlefish and squid (Brown, Garwood & Williamson, 2012; Schnell & Clayton, 2019).

Another example of complex cognition within a social setting includes the giant Australian cuttlefish, *Sepia apama*, which uses different fighting strategies like quickly changing from an aggressive to a submissive position or vice versa depending on the size of its enemy. The cognitive level for this is comparable to mammals and birds (Hanlon, Vecchione & Allcock, 2018). An aggressive position is adopted when the other animal is smaller, or a submissive position when it is larger. Medium and large sized males fight over females using aggressive or defensive behavior. Small males, on the other hand, avoid fights with larger males nearby through deceptive signaling, and may change their appearance to mimic females. This shows flexibilization of behavior, mental attribution and perspective that cuttlefish have of other individuals, as well as a certain level of self-awareness so that they understand which of the opponents is bigger or smaller than them (Mather & Dickel, 2017).

In addition to the four skills already mentioned, another form of intelligence measurement has been described by Thomas (1980), in which it is possible to rank an animal's intelligence within eight levels of complexity. Cephalopods are at level five, since they present the capacity for conditional discrimination as discussed by Hvorecny, et al. (2007).

Yet another way to measure the complex cognitive ability of animals is through mirror testing. When animals are placed in front of a mirror, they either exhibit social behavior (threat, curiosity) or ignore their reflection. Chimpanzees, orangutans, bottlenose dolphins, Asian elephants, and magpies exhibit self-directed (or self-monitoring) behavior towards their mirror image. They touch body parts with markings that would not be visible without the mirror, which indicates the ability of self-recognition in non-human animals and shows a potential that other animals could also have when presenting high social interactions and the necessary neural structures (Ikeda, 2009).

Squids (social animals) react in a highly social way. They show great interest in the reflection. Cuttlefish react in a semi-social way, with moderate interest in the reflection, touching the reflection image or acting defensively/aggressively. Octopi, on the other hand, do not have clear reactions, or do not move or go to the opposite side of the mirror to hide (Ikeda, 2009).

The octopi behavior is comparable to the behavior of gorillas that also do not react to their reflection in the mirror. This can be explained by the fact that gorillas do not look directly at other individuals in their group and therefore are not interested in looking at their own reflection even though they have self-awareness (Ikeda, 2009) as evidenced by Koko (Patterson & Linden, 1981). The same can be true for octopi, since they can use the image created in the mirror to see prey hidden behind a rock and hunt it down (Ikeda, 2009).

The self-perception described by Ikeda (2009), the decision-making made within a scenario of flexible behaviors (Schnell & Clayton, 2019), the use of tools with future planning (Mather, 1995), the ability to feel pain (Crook, 2021), the capacity for delayed gratification (Schnell, 2021a), the intentional behaviors to manipulate and deceive other individuals (Brown, Garwood & Williamson, 2012), the identification of causalities and understanding the effects of their actions, thus acting with intent, the creating of scenarios that are independent of the present such as mind maps, insights, and object permanence, the assessment of a situation and making different decisions according to the environment and the individuals around them, the showing of behavior plasticity (Schnell, 2021b), and, above all, the planning for the future through prospecting (Billard, et al., 2020) leads us to conclude that cephalopods have the so-called "theory of mind", which is the ability to make a mental attribution, to perceive the mental states of other individuals, their intentions, feelings, beliefs and desires (Jou & Superb, 1999) and act upon it. We can also conclude that they have the so-called "consciousness of higher order", defined by Eldman, Baars & Seth (2005) as the ability to present self-awareness, to reconstruct past scenarios and formulate future scenarios.

Much still needs to be studied in order to have a clearer picture of cephalopod capabilities, even if it is impossible to simulate the real richness of ecological and social stimuli and the challenges encountered by free-living animals. Therefore, researches such as those consulted in this literary review are extremely important for the education of the general public and to raise awareness about the conservation of these animals and their habitats.

4. Conclusion

Studies show that coleoid cephalopods are capable of displaying various cognitive abilities such as association learning, discrimination learning, advanced spatial learning, exploratory learning, social learning, reverse associative learning, rapid taste aversion learning, reverse learning, facultative communication, future-oriented behavior,

appetitive conditioning, visual discrimination, conditional, tactile, species discrimination, tactical deception, behavioral flexibility, delayed gratification, identification of individual humans, imprinting, short-term and long-term memory, source and episodic memory, mimicry, individual personalities, object permanence, number sense, tool use and mirror identification.

These abilities within ecological and social contexts become tools for complex cognition behaviors. Behaviors that can also be identified in different groups of vertebrates considered intelligent, such as primates, corvids and cetaceans. With this set of complex cognitive skills, it is possible to conclude that these invertebrate animals, coleoid cephalopods, possess a level five intelligence, higher order consciousness and theory of mind.

It will never be clear exactly what it means to be an octopus, squid, or cuttlefish, but their abilities and behaviors which make them highly adaptable to different types of environments and situations are impressive enough to be able to sensitize the general population and raise awareness that they are moved enough to help fight for their conservation.

5. References

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